

SceneSplat: Gaussian Splatting-based Scene Understanding with Vision-Language Pretraining

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Figure 1. We present the 3DGS indoor dataset **SceneSplat-7K** which includes 7K scenes generated from ARKitScenes [1], Replica [46], ScanNet [5], ScanNet++ [57], Hypersim[43], 3RScan [49], and Matterport3D [2]. Leveraging this high-quality dataset, we propose **SceneSplat**, the first model to predict open-vocabulary language features for millions of 3D Gaussians in a single forward pass.

Abstract

Recognizing arbitrary or previously unseen categories is essential for comprehensive real-world 3D scene understanding. Currently, all existing methods rely on 2D or textual modalities during training or together at inference. This highlights the clear absence of a model capable of processing 3D data alone for learning semantics end-to-end, along with the necessary data to train such a model. Meanwhile, 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) has emerged as the de facto standard for 3D scene representation across various vision tasks. However, effectively integrating semantic reasoning into 3DGS in a generalizable manner remains an open challenge. To address these limitations, we introduce *SceneSplat* in Fig. 1, to our knowledge the first large-scale 3D indoor scene understanding approach that operates natively on 3DGS. Furthermore, we propose a self-supervised

learning scheme that unlocks rich 3D feature learning from unlabeled scenes. To power the proposed methods, we introduce *SceneSplat-7K*, the first large-scale 3DGS dataset for indoor scenes, comprising 7916 scenes derived from seven established datasets, such as ScanNet and Matterport3D. Generating *SceneSplat-7K* required computational resources equivalent to 150 GPU days on an L4 GPU, enabling standardized benchmarking for 3DGS-based reasoning for indoor scenes. Our exhaustive experiments on *SceneSplat-7K* demonstrate the significant benefit of the proposed method over the established baselines. Our code, model, and datasets will be released at [SceneSplat](#).

1. Introduction

The ability to interpret arbitrary queries rather than being limited to a closed set of categories is crucial for 3D understanding models to generalize across diverse real-world scenarios. Traditional 3D vision systems are typically trained on fixed closed-set category labels drawn from datasets like ScanNet [5]. Such label spaces fail to capture the diver-

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sity of concepts in real-world environments. This gap has spurred significant interest in open-vocabulary 3D scene understanding, which aims to recognize arbitrary or unseen categories beyond a predefined taxonomy [8, 15, 54]. Achieving this capability would empower the model to reason about novel objects in a scene using natural language descriptors.

Achieving open-vocabulary recognition in 3D is challenging due to the scarcity of large-scale 3D-text paired data. Breakthroughs in 2D vision, driven by internet-scale image-text pre-training, cannot be directly leveraged in 3D due to the absence of analogous 3D datasets with rich textual annotations. To address this gap, current methods resort to multi-modality fusion, distilling knowledge from 2D vision-language models into 3D data. Some approaches project 3D points into source images and use a pretrained 2D backbone (e.g., CLIP) to supervise 3D feature learning [34, 64, 70]; others generate synthetic captions for 3D scenes to explicitly associate point clouds with semantic-rich text [7, 44]. However, all current methods rely on 2D or textual modalities during training, or together at inference, to compensate for limited 3D semantics. This highlights a key limitation: *the absence of a robust model for processing 3D data end-to-end for semantic learning*, along with *the lack of sufficient data for training such a model*.

The field of 3D representation is rapidly evolving. While classical 3D networks rely on point clouds or voxel grids [50, 51, 55], recent approaches inspired by radiance fields have greatly improved scene representation. Notably, 3D Gaussian Splatting (3DGS) [16] has emerged as an efficient representation, achieving state-of-the-art performance in view synthesis and geometry modeling [58, 61]. Unlike discrete point clouds, 3DGS provides a compact formulation that can be optimized per scene for 2D synthesis, while the underlying Gaussians also softly encode rich 3D structures (positions, shapes, and opacities of the regions). This makes it a unique candidate for 3D scene cues, as it naturally fuses geometry and appearance information. However, integrating semantic reasoning into 3DGS is nontrivial. The naïve way of optimizing additional semantic features in 3DGS [17] is inefficient and limited to a single scene. Consequently, generalizable open-vocabulary understanding in 3DGS remains unexplored, as no existing model directly processes 3D Gaussian parameters. Moreover, no large-scale scene-level 3DGS dataset is available to train such models, further limiting the progress in this direction.

We address these limitations with SceneSplat, to our knowledge the first large-scale 3D indoor scene understanding approach that operates natively on 3D Gaussian splats. The proposed model is powered by SceneSplat-7K, a carefully curated 3DGS indoor scene dataset spanning around 7K scenes. SceneSplat introduces a 3DGS encoder that takes as input the parameters of a Gaussian-splat scene (cen-

ter, scale, color, opacity) and outputs semantic features in a per-primitive manner, in a single forward pass. We leverage supervision from vision-language models to train SceneSplat’s encoder to produce CLIP-aligned embeddings, effectively bridging language and 3D without explicit 2D fusion at runtime. Furthermore, we propose GaussSSL, a self-supervised learning scheme that unlocks rich 3D feature learning from unlabeled scenes. GaussSSL operates through three synergistic strategies: Masked Gaussian Modeling (MGM), self-distillation, and optional Language-Gaussian Feature Alignment, allowing the model to separate high-level semantic signals from raw parameters alone. This self-supervised pretraining is fueled by large amounts of 3DGS scenes in the SceneSplat-7K dataset. Our contributions can be summarized as follows:

- We present SceneSplat-7K, a high-quality large-scale Gaussian splats dataset spanning 7K indoor scenes, which boosts 3DGS scene understanding research.
- We propose SceneSplat, a model that unlocks open-vocabulary recognition for 3D Gaussian splats and achieves state-of-the-art zero-shot semantic segmentation performance on three fine-grained benchmarks.
- We incorporate annotation-free self-supervised training mechanisms on this large-scale indoor dataset and demonstrate their effectiveness in the downstream indoor segmentation task.

2. Related Work

3D Indoor Datasets. The advancement of 3D deep learning has driven the development of various indoor datasets for scene understanding, reconstruction, and representation learning [1, 2, 5, 43, 46, 49, 57]. ScanNet [5] serves as a fundamental benchmark with 1,513 real-world indoor scenes and dense annotations, while ScanNet++ [57] extends it with additional real and synthetic scenes. HyperSim [43] offers photorealistic synthetic environments, and ARKitScenes [1] captures 1,661 real-world indoor scenes using ARKit. Replica [46] provides high-fidelity reconstructions, and 3RScan [49] supports multi-view analysis with 1,482 scans. Habitat-Matterport3D [2] integrates Matterport3D into an embodied AI simulation platform. These datasets are essential for 3D perception but lack large-scale support for emerging 3D representations like 3DGS. Prior works [13, 28] have explored NeRF-based representations, and ShapeSplat [27] introduced Gaussian-splatted objects, but no dataset currently supports indoor scene understanding with Gaussian Splatting. To address this limitation, we introduce a 3D Gaussian Splatting scene dataset derived from 7 widely used indoor datasets [1, 2, 5, 43, 46, 49, 57]. Our dataset offers a rich collection of indoor scenes from both real-world and synthetic sources, featuring high-quality Gaussian splats, facilitating the transition from object-level to scene-level Gaussian splatting and ad-

Metric	ScanNet[5]	ScanNet++[57]	ScanNet++v2[57]	Replica[46]	Hypersim[43]	3RScan[49]	ARKitScenes[1]	Matterport3D[2]	SceneSplat-7K
Raw Scenes	1613	380	1006	8	461	1482(scans)	1970	2194(regions)	9114
GS Scenes	1613	330	956	8	448	632(scans)	1947	1982(regions)	7916
RGB Frames	2.5M	228K	1.1M	16K	77K	156K	450K	194K	4.72M
Storage	600GB	152GB	447GB	7GB	251GB	235GB	577GB	492GB	2.76TB
PSNR	29.07	29.49	29.11	41.25	25.93	27.46	29.18	32.34	29.64
Depth Loss	0.031	0.019	0.015	0.002	0.228	0.018	0.0131	0.033	0.035
SSIM	0.869	0.924	0.933	0.980	0.894	0.881	0.885	0.916	0.897
LPIPS	0.236	0.133	0.116	0.0396	0.157	0.335	0.294	0.145	0.212
GS per scene	1.50M	1.56M	1.89M	1.50M	2.84M	1.50M	1.19M	1.0M	1.42M
Total GS	2419.5M	513.4M	1810.3M	12.0M	1,237.5M	948.0M	2,316.9M	1,982M	11.27B
GPU Time (L4)	593h	177h	594h	4h	176h	576h	811h	661h	3592 h

Table 1. **Dataset Statistics.** The proposed SceneSplat-7K dataset includes various 3D Gaussian Splatting datasets generated from ScanNet [5], ScanNet++ [57], ScanNet++ v2, Replica[46], Hypersim[43], 3RScan[49], ARKitScenes[1], and Matterport3D[2]. The dataset contains **7,916 scenes** and **11.27 Billion 3DGS**. Constructing this dataset required computational resources equivalent to **150 GPU days** on one NVIDIA L4 GPU. SceneSplat-7K achieves high-fidelity reconstruction quality with an average PSNR **29.64 dB**.

vancing large-scale 3D scene understanding.

Open Vocabulary Scene Understanding. Recent advancements in open-vocabulary models have significantly expanded the capabilities of vision-language understanding. Foundation models such as DINO [32, 62] have enabled self-supervised visual feature extraction at scale, effectively supporting tasks like detection and segmentation. SAM [20, 40] introduced the capability of prompt-driven segmentation, generalizing robustly across diverse datasets and tasks. CLIP [38] pioneered aligning visual and textual embedding spaces, allowing for zero-shot transfer across numerous downstream tasks. Subsequently, SigLIP [47, 60] improved alignment by introducing non-linear activation techniques, enhancing open-vocabulary performance marginally. Recent works [4, 10, 34, 37, 67, 69] have also introduced 2D open-vocabulary foundation models into 3D by utilizing NeRF [31] or 3DGS [16]. LERF [17, 39] integrated language queries into NeRF-based models, enabling rich semantic querying within 3D scenes. LangSplat [37] combined 3DGS with open-vocabulary embeddings from SAM [40] and CLIP [38], facilitating open-vocabulary semantic scene understanding. OccamLGS [4] further optimized this process by employing feature lifting, directly projecting all 2D features into 3DGS, and reducing computation time from hours to seconds. However, these methods require time-consuming preprocessing of images using 2D foundation models. In contrast, we propose a pipeline and dataset for training a 3D foundation model, enabling feed-forward open-vocabulary understanding of 3DGS.

3D Representation Learning. Representation learning in 3D, akin to its success in the 2D image domain, is crucial for extracting meaningful features from 3D data. Previous approaches have focused on either architectural advancements or learning paradigms. Many methods have sought to map 3D data into 2D patches, leveraging conventional 2D CNNs or Vision Transformers [9, 29, 30, 41, 48]. Although promising, this approach often overlooks the inherent properties of 3D data due to the embedding strategy. To

address this, research has shifted toward specialized architectures (*i.e.*, PointCNN [22], PointNet [35], Point Transformer [50, 51, 65], and Pointmamba [24]). However, labeling 3D data requires extensive effort and domain expertise, making it quite challenging. This has highlighted the importance of self-supervised learning (SSL) for 3D data, with methods typically falling into contrastive or generative categories. Contrastive methods aim to differentiate similar and dissimilar examples, but often suffer from issues such as overfitting and mode collapse, exacerbated by the sparse nature of 3D data [36, 42]. On the other hand, generative methods, inspired by BERT’s *mask-and-reconstruct* strategy [6], have proven more effective. Masked Autoencoders [11], originally designed for 2D images, have been adapted for 3D data types, including point clouds [33, 63], meshes [25], voxels [12], and Gaussians [27], allowing the reconstruction of masked regions and facilitating the learning of robust spatial and semantic features. In this work, we propose a novel approach for vision-language 3DGS pre-training, as well as a self-supervised learning scheme that operates via Gaussian masking and self-distillation.

3. SceneSplat Dataset

We introduce SceneSplat-7K – a carefully curated dataset of 3D Gaussian Splats representing indoor scenes. The main goal was to obtain a dataset to facilitate generalizable 3DGS indoor scene understanding. The dataset contains about seven thousand scenes, including both real-world and synthetic environments. The comprehensive statistics of the introduced dataset are presented in Tab. 1. The SceneSplat-7K dataset will be publicly released, with additional details (licenses) available in the supplement.

3.1. Data Processing

Multiple measures are applied before, during, and after the 3DGS optimization to guarantee high-quality 3DGS scenes. Starting with the training views, we select scenes with at least 400 frames to ensure sufficient multi-view coverage.

We remove blurry frames by using the variance of the Laplacian as a sharpness metric. We use gsplat [56] for 3DGS optimization. For scenes with available depth input, we apply depth loss to achieve better geometry modeling. To efficiently compress the 3DGS scene, we employ a Markov Chain Monte Carlo strategy [18] and add opacity and scale regularization. Once optimized, we filtered 3DGS scenes based on the PSNR metric before using them as inputs for our pretraining. We refer to the supplement for per-dataset processing details.

3.2. Data Statistic

SceneSplat-7K dataset includes various 3D Gaussian Splatting datasets generated from ScanNet [5], ScanNet++ [57], ScanNet++ v2, Replica [46], Hypersim [43], 3RScan [49], ARKitScenes [1], and Matterport3D [2], comprising approximately 9,000 raw scenes. SceneSplat-7K contains **7,916** processed Gaussian splatting scenes, with an average of 1.42 Million 3D Gaussians per scene and **11.27 Billion Gaussians** in total, from which 4,114 high-quality Gaussian splatting scenes are selected for pretraining. Spanning a total of 4.72 Million RGB frames, SceneSplat-7K achieves high-fidelity appearance and competitive reconstruction quality, having an average PSNR of 29.64 dB, average depth loss of 0.035 m, average SSIM of 0.897, and average LPIPS of 0.212. Constructing this dataset required an equivalent of **150 days** of computation on an NVIDIA L4 GPU.

4. Methodology

Building upon the SceneSplat-7K dataset, we carry out both vision-language 3DGS pretraining, which enables open-vocabulary scene understanding, and self-supervised pretraining, which regularizes the latent space during 3DGS parameter encoding, as shown in Fig. 2. For vision-language pretraining, we first need to collect primitive-level language labels for 3DGS scenes (Sec. 4.1). The SceneSplat model then learns to robustly predict vision-language features from the Gaussian parameters and their surroundings (Sec. 4.2). Furthermore, for self-supervised pretraining, we employ a multi-objective self-supervised training framework that integrates reconstruction and self-distillation alignment (Sec. 4.3).

4.1. 3DGS Language Label Collection

Our language label collection aims to establish 3D-language paired data by associating each 3D Gaussian primitive G_i with a rich semantic feature $F_i \in \mathbb{R}^d$.

Unlike methods that align 3D primitives with text embeddings [8, 21] or use visual captioning [26, 59], we directly align Gaussians with the image embedding space of vision-language models (VLM), preserving richer latent

Algorithm 1 3DGS Language Label Collection

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1: Input: Training views  $\{I_j\}_{j=1}^M$ , 3D Gaussian scene  $\{G_i\}_{i=1}^N$ , SAMv2, SigLip2
2: Output: 3D Gaussian-feature pairs  $\{(G_i, F_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ 
3: Step 1: 2D Feature Map Generation
4: for each training view  $I_j$  do
5:    $M_{\text{seg}} \leftarrow \text{SAMv2}(I_j)$   $\triangleright$  Get object-level seg. masks
6:    $f_g \leftarrow \text{SigLip2}(I_j)$   $\triangleright$  Feature from full frame
7:   Initialize feature map  $F_j$  for view  $I_j$ 
8:   for each segment  $s$  in  $M_{\text{seg}}$  do
9:      $f_l, f_m \leftarrow \text{SigLip2}(\text{crop}(I_j, s))$ 
10:     $\triangleright$  Local features for crops w/ and w/o background
11:    Dynamic Weighting:
12:     $w_g, w_l, w_m \leftarrow \text{compute\_weights}(f_g, f_l, f_m)$ 
13:     $\triangleright$  Weights based on context
14:     $f_s \leftarrow w_g \cdot f_g + w_l \cdot f_l + w_m \cdot f_m$ 
15:     $\triangleright$  Fuse features
16:    Update feature map  $F_j$  with  $f_s$  at segment  $s$ 
17:  end for
18: end for
19: Step 2: Lifting 2D Features to 3D Gaussian Feature Field
20:  $\{F_i\}_{i=1}^N \leftarrow \text{Occam's LGS}(\{F_j\}_{j=1}^M, \{G_i\}_{i=1}^N)$   $\triangleright$  Lift 2D features to 3D
21:  $\{F_i\}_{i=1}^N \leftarrow \text{normalize}(\{F_i\}_{i=1}^N)$   $\triangleright$  Normalization
22: Return: 3D Gaussian-feature pairs  $\{(G_i, F_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ 

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semantic information. Our approach also avoids scene-specific compression [37, 45] which limits scalability and generalization.

As outlined in Alg. 1, we employ SAMv2 [40] for object-level segmentation and SigLIP2 [47] for feature extraction. We then use Occam’s LGS [4] to efficiently lift these 2D feature maps to a 3D Gaussian feature field in an optimization-free manner. This results in a comprehensive collection of 3DGS-feature pairs $\{(G_i, F_i)\}_{i=1}^N$ across multiple datasets, providing a solid foundation for our vision-language pretraining.

4.2. Vision-Language 3DGS Pretraining

We first adapt the transformer encoder-decoder backbone from [51] to efficiently predict high-dimensional per-primitive features corresponding to collected 3DGS language labels. More specifically, our model $g(\cdot)$, parameterized by θ , maps the input Gaussians to their language features:

$$\hat{F} = g_{\theta}(\{G_i\}_{i=1}^N), \quad (1)$$

where $\hat{F} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times d}$ is the predicted per-gaussian feature.

We apply three training objectives for supervision. The cosine similarity loss minimizes the angular difference be-

Figure 2. **SceneSplat Overview.** The SceneSplat-7K dataset enables **Vision-Language Pretraining** and **Self-Supervised Pretraining**. For vision-language pretraining, we associate each 3D Gaussian primitive with semantic features based on our label collection process and train a generalizable open-vocabulary learner that predict per-gaussian embeddings. For self-supervised pretraining, we employ Masked Gaussian Modeling to reconstruct masked primitives, Self-Distillation Learning for augmentation-invariant features, and Language-Gaussian Alignment for scenes with collected labels. The former achieves state-of-the-art zero-shot segmentation results on ScanNet200 [5], ScanNet++ [57], and Matterport3D [2] benchmarks and the latter unlocks training on large-scale 3DGS data.

tween the predicted and ground truth language labels:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{cos}} = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \left(1 - \frac{\hat{F}_i \cdot F_i}{\|\hat{F}_i\| \cdot \|F_i\|} \right), \quad (2)$$

where \mathcal{V} is the set of Gaussians with language feature labels. To enforce feature similarity in Euclidean space, we use L2 loss:

$$\mathcal{L}_2 = \frac{1}{|\mathcal{V}|} \sum_{i \in \mathcal{V}} \|\hat{F}_i - F_i\|^2. \quad (3)$$

Lastly, we use an aggregated contrastive loss to encourage the separation of class-level features. Instead of contrasting every Gaussian feature individually (which would be computationally prohibitive in large scenes), we apply class-wise *mean pooling*. For each semantic class c with sufficiently many Gaussians, we randomly split its Gaussians into two disjoint sets \mathcal{G}_c^A and \mathcal{G}_c^B , and compute the pooled features:

$$\bar{F}_c^A = \text{Pool}(\hat{F}, \mathcal{G}_c^A), \quad \bar{F}_c^B = \text{Pool}(\hat{F}, \mathcal{G}_c^B). \quad (4)$$

We then apply a bidirectional contrastive loss. First, we normalize \bar{F}_c^A and \bar{F}_c^B to unit length. Let $Z^A = \bar{F}_c^A (\bar{F}_c^B)^\top / \tau$ and $Z^B = \bar{F}_c^B (\bar{F}_c^A)^\top / \tau$, where each row in \bar{F}_c^A or \bar{F}_c^B corresponds to a different semantic class. The diagonal elements of Z^A and Z^B are positive matches. Hence, we compute a cross-entropy loss in both directions:

$$\mathcal{L}_{\text{contrast}} = \frac{1}{2|C|} \sum_{X \in \{A, B\}} \sum_{i \in C} -\log \frac{\exp(Z_{i,i}^X)}{\sum_{j \in C} \exp(Z_{i,j}^X)}, \quad (5)$$

where C is the set of semantic classes with sufficient Gaussians, τ is a learnable temperature controlling the softness of the distribution.

The total loss is the weighted sum $\mathcal{L}_{\text{total}} = \lambda_{\text{cos}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{cos}} + \lambda_{\text{L2}} \mathcal{L}_2 + \lambda_{\text{con}} \mathcal{L}_{\text{contrast}}$, where $\lambda(\cdot)$ denotes each weight. In practice, we found that applying the contrastive loss later during the training (*i.e.*, “warm starting” with \mathcal{L}_{cos} and \mathcal{L}_2) helps promote early feature learning while effectively refining class distinctions in later stages.

Through this training, our model learns to predict semantically rich language features for each Gaussian primitive, enabling downstream open-vocabulary scene understanding task without requiring additional finetuning or 2D input.

4.3. Self Supervised Pretraining

The proposed GaussianSSL method is presented in Fig. 2 (right). It incorporates multiple losses with different objectives into SceneSplat’s large-scale pretraining.

Masked Gaussian Modeling. This part supervises the model to predict masked Gaussian primitives. Given a 3D Gaussian splatting scene represented by $\mathcal{G} = \{G_i\}_{i=1}^N$, where $G_i \in \mathbb{R}^{59}$, the training proceeds as follows: (1) A subset $\{G_j\}_{j=1}^{N'}$ is sampled from \mathcal{G} using dense grid sampling of size S . (2) Samples are projected into a latent space with the embedding function P to obtain tokens $E = P(\{G_j\}_{j=1}^{N'}) \in \mathbb{R}^{N' \times d_e}$, where d_e is the embedding dimension. (3) The tokens E are masked with ratio $r \in [0, 1]$ by replacing $N' \cdot r$ randomly chosen tokens with a learnable mask token $t \in \mathbb{R}^{d_e}$ to obtain $T_m \in \mathbb{R}^{N' \times d_e}$. (4) The masked tokens T_m are processed using the 3D backbone $g_\theta(\cdot)$ to obtain $\hat{T}_m = h_\phi(f_\varphi(T_m))$, where $f_\varphi(\cdot)$ is the encoder and $h_\phi(\cdot)$ is the decoder. (5) The output tokens \hat{T}_m are mapped to the input Gaussian space with the reconstruction projector $\hat{G}_m = \Phi(\hat{T}_m) \in \mathbb{R}^{N' \times F}$. (6) Finally, the \mathcal{L}_2 reconstruction loss between the predicted masked Gaussians and the original Gaussians is used: $\mathcal{L}_{\text{MGM}} = \mathbb{E}_{G_j \sim \mathcal{G}} [\|G_m - \hat{G}_m\|_2^2]$.

Self-Distillation Representation Learning. Self-distillation [32] learns augmentation-invariant representations by aligning the predictions of a student network θ_s with an EMA-updated teacher θ_t [3]. For a batch of Gaussian scenes $\{\mathcal{G}_n\}_{n=1}^B$ (global/local views G_g^b, G_l^b), we extract tokenized bottleneck features $z \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times d_e}$, compute global representations \bar{z} via mean pooling, and align student-teacher outputs via cosine similarity loss \mathcal{L}_{sim} [52]. Feature diversity is regularized with a coding rate term \mathcal{L}_{cr} [23, 52] resulting in $\mathcal{L}_{\text{DINO}} = \omega_{\text{sim}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{sim}} + \omega_{\text{cr}}\mathcal{L}_{\text{cr}}$ with corresponding weights. Inspired by [52, 68], the student network also predicts masked features aligned with the teacher via $\mathcal{L}_{\text{iBOT}}$, computed using cosine similarity. We propose to mitigate the decoder collapse issues by multi-task reconstruction \mathcal{L}_{MGM} , as coding rate regularization stabilizes only the hierarchical encoder. Following [11, 53], the reconstruction is limited to weakly augmented views to avoid degradation.

Language-Gaussian Alignment. As shown in Sec. 4.2, the precomputed language feature enables effective knowledge distillation. For scenes with existing language labels, we seek to leverage them to further regulate self-supervised learning. However, the high dimensionality of these language features (dimension $N \times d_L$) can substantially increase the computational cost of supervision. To address this, we replace the original features with a compressed representation learned via an autoencoder [19], drastically reducing the memory overhead while preserving semantic information. Similar to \mathcal{L}_{MGM} , we use \mathcal{L}_{LA} following Eqs. (2) and (3) to train the network to predict low-dimensional language features from unmasked neighbors.

5. Experiments

In this section, we evaluate the performance of vision-language pretraining on open-vocabulary task and examine the impact of large-scale Gaussian self-supervised pretraining on downstream indoor semantic segmentation. We further justify our design choices through ablation studies. The implementation details are provided in the supplement.

5.1. Vision-Language Pretraining

Tab. 2 reports the zero-shot 3D semantic segmentation results on the fine-grained ScanNet++ (100 classes) [57], Matterport3D (160 classes) [2] and ScanNet200 (200 classes) [5] benchmarks, where methods are trained on specified data sources. When trained on ScanNet, SceneSplat achieves state-of-the-art results, leading to 5.9% and 2.2% f-mIoU increases on the ScanNet200 and Matterport3D benchmarks. By extending the training sources, we obtain 5.7%, 0.7%, and 10.4% f-mIoU increases on the ScanNet200, Matterport3D, and ScanNet++ benchmarks, respectively, compared to concurrent work [21]. Notably, [21] uses $8.32 \times$ training scenes to achieve its best results,

Figure 3. **Qualitative Results of Zero-Shot 3D Semantic Segmentation on ScanNet++.** SceneSplat demonstrates competitive zero-shot performance, note how our model correctly annotate the regions lacking ground truth labels, *e.g.*, desks on the top row. Best viewed zoomed in and in color.

Figure 4. **Text-Based 3DGS Scene Query.** Given text queries and SceneSplat inference results for a 3DGS scene, we can effectively localize the corresponding splats in 3D (highlighted in red for queries "Robot Arm", "Box", and "Keyboard").

indicating that transferring 2D vision-language priors via 3DGS is a superior strategy.

Fig. 3 shows the zero-shot segmentation results on evaluation scenes. SceneSplat not only achieves competitive segmentation performance but also correctly annotates the missing semantic labels (*e.g.*, desks shown above). We demonstrate text-based queries on the inference results of the predicted language features in Fig. 4. Our vision-language pretraining enables the effective localization of complex objects within the scene.

5.2. Label-free 3DGS Pretraining

We conduct extensive pretraining experiments with the proposed GaussianSSL method. To assess the efficacy of the pretrained model, we report the segmentation results in Tab. 3. Our method achieves a +0.1% improvement over supervised-only baselines on ScanNet20 and +0.5% on ScanNet200, while observing a performance drop on ScanNet++ primarily due to pretraining dataset quality variations

Method	Training Source	#Training Scenes	ScanNet200 (200)		Matterport3D (160)		ScanNet++ (100)	
			f-mIoU	f-mAcc	f-mIoU	f-mAcc	f-mIoU	f-mAcc
OpenScene [†] [34]	SN	×1	6.4	12.2	5.7	10.7	8.8	14.7
PLA [8]	SN	–	1.8	3.1	–	–	–	–
RegionPLC [54]	SN	–	9.2	16.4	6.2	13.3	11.3	20.1
OV3D [15]	SN	–	8.7	–	–	–	–	–
Mosaic3D [21]	SN	–	<u>13.0</u>	<u>24.5</u>	<u>8.6</u>	<u>17.8</u>	16.2	27.1
SceneSplat (Ours)	SN	–	18.9	31.7	10.8	18.7	<u>14.7</u>	<u>24.7</u>
Mosaic3D [21]	SN, SN++, ARKitS, MP3D, S3D	×24.3	<u>15.7</u>	<u>28.3</u>	<u>13.1</u>	<u>27.7</u>	18.0	29.0
SceneSplat (Ours)	SN++	×0.75	11.8	19.2	10.6	18.6	<u>26.8</u>	<u>45.3</u>
SceneSplat (Ours)	SN, SN++, MP3D	×2.92	21.4	38.7	13.8	31.8	28.4	50.0

Table 2. **Zero-Shot 3D Semantic Segmentation on the Fine-Grained ScanNet++ (100 classes) [57], Matterport3D (160 classes) [2] and ScanNet200 (200 classes) [5] Benchmarks.** We report the foreground mean IoU (f-mIoU) and foreground mean accuracy (f-mAcc) excluding background classes (wall, floor, ceiling), following [8, 14, 34, 54]. [†] denotes the official checkpoint and the results of the baselines are taken from [21]. Dataset abbreviations SN, SN++, ARKitS, MP3D, and S3D respectively denote ScanNet [5], ScanNet++ [57], ARKitScenes [1], Matterport3D [2] and Structured3D [66]. SceneSplat achieves noticeably better segmentation performance, *i.e.*, a 5.9% f-mIoU increase on the ScanNet200 benchmark when trained on a single source, and an 10.4% f-mIoU increase on ScanNet++ when trained on three sources, while using significantly less training data compared to the concurrent work [21].

Method	ScanNet20 (20)		ScanNet200 (200)		ScanNet++ (100)	
	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc
No-Pre	<u>77.1</u>	84.1	35.4	44.0	42.4	53.3
MGM	76.7	83.5	<u>35.5</u>	<u>44.5</u>	41.7	51.9
+DINO	77.0	84.6	35.9	46.1	<u>42.0</u>	<u>52.4</u>
+iBOT	77.2	<u>84.2</u>	35.2	44.3	41.1	52.0
+LA	77.2	<u>84.2</u>	34.7	44.4	41.4	52.5

Table 3. **GaussianSSL Ablation Experiments.** We adopt the pre-training on the SceneSplat-7K dataset and report fine-tuning mIoU and mAcc on indoor semantic segmentation tasks. For details of specific losses please refer to Sec. 4.3 and Fig. 2.

Method	ScanNet20		ScanNet200		ScanNet++	
	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc
PTv1 [65]	70.6	—	27.8	—	—	—
PTv2 [50]	75.4	—	30.2	—	—	—
PTv3 [51]	76.4	83.5	35.0	44.2	42.6	53.0
SceneSplat (Ours)	77.2	84.6	35.9	46.1	42.4	53.5

Table 4. **Supervised Semantic Segmentation Experiments.** We report our best results from Tab. 3 comparing against the state-of-the-art Point Transformer method.

(Tab. 1). Furthermore, compared with our reproduced implementation of PTv3 [51], we outperform by +0.8% on ScanNet20 and +0.9% on ScanNet200 (Tab. 4). More qualitative results are provided in the supplement.

5.3. Further Statistical Evaluation

SceneSplat Inference Results vs. Collected Language Labels. One may assume that the collected language labels cap the upper bound zero-shot performance since they provide the supervision signal during vision-language pretraining. Interestingly, this is not always the case. Tab. 5 compares the performance of SceneSplat inference features with the collected language labels. On ScanNet++, our method

Method	ScanNet200		ScanNet++		Matterport3D	
	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc
Training Data	22.8	35.9	22.6	46.5	11.5	28.0
SceneSplat (Ours)	21.4	38.7	28.4	50.0	13.8	31.8

Table 5. **SceneSplat Inference Results vs. Collected Language Labels on Zero-Shot 3D Semantic Segmentation.** The result on ScanNet++ shows the inference performance can be even better than using the collected labels. SceneSplat here is trained on the single dataset respectively.

Figure 5. **Distribution of SceneSplat Zero-Shot Semantic Segmentation mIoU w.r.t. Input 3DGS Scene PSNR.** Reported on the Matterport3D test split labeled in 21 semantic classes, the box plot shows a clear positive trend between the input 3DGS scene training PSNR and the resulted mIoU once applied SceneSplat language pretraining for zero-shot semantic segmentation. This encourages the careful curation of the collected 3DGS scene dataset.

outperforms the labels with a 4.2% increase in f-mIoU. Although the collected labels are not perfect, large-scale pretraining can filter noise and learn meaningful patterns.

Impact of the Input 3DGS Scene PSNR on Open-

Figure 6. **Overall and Class-Wise IoU Changes *w.r.t.* to the Nearest Neighbor Number During Majority Voting.** We evaluate SceneSplat using different number of nearest 3DGS neighbors for zero-shot task on ScanNet++ validation split. Overall mIoU increases with different class-wise relative IoU changes.

Vocabulary Performance. Reported on the Matterport3D test split with 370 scenes, Fig. 5 indicates a clear positive trend of the input 3DGS scene PSNR of the training views and the resulting zero-shot mIoU performance with SceneSplat model. Low PSNRs usually come out of blurry input images, poor Gaussian centers optimization, and insufficient scene coverage, where the 3DGS parameters cannot resolve the scene well. This trend highlights the importance of data curation for the collected 3DGS scenes.

Training data	#Scenes	ScanNet++	ScanNet200
SN++ v1	280	22.99 / 39.24	10.81 / 16.50
SN++ v2	906	26.40 / 43.98	11.43 / 18.76
SN++ v2 + SN	2107	27.79 / 50.55	14.27 / 34.34
SN++ v2 + SN + MP3D	3503	28.36 / 49.92	16.48 / 35.73

Table 6. **Data Scaling Experiments** (f-mIoU / f-mAcc [%]).

SceneSplat Training Input	ScanNet200 (200)		ScanNet++ (100)	
	mIoU	mAcc	mIoU	mAcc
Point Parameters	17.1	27.9	23.8	40.2
3DGS Parameters	18.9	31.7	26.8	45.3

Table 7. **Zero-Shot Performance of Using Point Clouds vs. 3DGS for SceneSplat Vision-Language Pretraining.** SceneSplat trained on 3DGS parameters consistently outperforms the variant trained on point cloud properties. The models here are trained on the single dataset respectively.

Contrastive Loss	ScanNet200 (200)		ScanNet++ (100)	
	f-mIoU	f-mAcc	f-mIoU	f-mAcc
w/o	13.7	22.5	19.6	34.4
always apply	13.2	23.4	23.2	39.3
last 75% epochs	15.7	24.0	23.8	40.2

Table 8. **Ablation on Contrastive Loss During Vision-Language Pretraining Using Subsets.** Having a warm-up period and applying the contrastive loss later leads to better performance.

Data Scaling Experiments. Tab. 6 presents scaling results

Method	Steps Required	Runtime / Scene
Occam’s LGS	2D fusion + lifting	107 min
SceneSplat	single inference	0.24 min

Table 9. **Runtime.** SceneSplat is significantly faster compared to the current fastest language-embedded 3DGS method.

on *training data*. Our vision-language pretraining effectively benefits from more data, highlighting the importance of our dataset for training a generalizable method.

Nearest Neighbors Voting During Zero-Shot Experiments. The centers of the input Gaussians differ from the point locations where the semantic predictions are evaluated; thus, we have to aggregate predictions from neighboring Gaussians. We perform majority voting using the nearest neighboring Gaussians for each evaluation location. Fig. 6 ablates the number of nearest neighbors on the IoU results using the ScanNet++ validation split. We observe the overall trend of the mIoU increase *w.r.t.* to the number of nearest neighbors and list the classes with the top relative changes. To balance the performance and inference speed, 25 nearest neighbors are selected for voting.

Effectiveness of Using 3DGS in Vision-Language Pretraining Compared to Point Clouds. To further justify the effectiveness of using 3DGS parameters for scene understanding, we apply the same vision-language pretraining on point properties (color and normal). Tab. 7 indicates that the model takes point properties as input consistently get outperformed by SceneSplat using 3DGS parameters.

Ablation on Contrastive Loss in the Vision-Language Pretraining. Tab. 8 ablates the contrastive loss applied during vision-language pretraining, where applying contrastive loss at the late stage of training outperforms other variants.

Runtime vs. Per-Scene Language Gaussian Splatting Method. Thanks to the feed-forward ability after vision-language pretraining, SceneSplat is shown in Tab. 9 to be $445.8\times$ faster than the state-of-the-art language-embedded Gaussian Splatting method, as there is no need for 2D feature extraction and fusion.

6. Conclusion

In this work, we introduce SceneSplat, the first large-scale 3D scene understanding model for indoor environments operating directly on 3D Gaussian splats. Powered by SceneSplat-7K, a dataset comprising 7,916 scenes, we propose a novel 3D Gaussian splat encoder that generates semantic features in a single pass, enabling open-vocabulary scene recognition without relying on 2D fusion. Through self-supervised techniques, we unlock label-free 3DGS pretraining at the scene level. Our approach achieves state-of-the-art performance in zero-shot semantic segmentation, establishing new benchmarks and laying the foundation for future advancements in open-vocabulary 3D understanding.

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